

HiRustVer: Industrial Rust Verification via Mature C Toolchains

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Rust is increasingly adopted in mission-critical systems, yet its type system alone cannot prevent panics, logic errors, or undefined behavior from unsafe code—formal verification remains necessary. However, real-world industrial Rust codebases pose three key challenges for verification: pervasive use of advanced features (associated types, dynamic dispatch, closures, unsafe blocks), complex dependency graphs with over a hundred transitive crates, and stringent industrial constraints where code rewriting is infeasible and automation is essential. No existing Rust verification tool meets these combined requirements. We present HiRustVer, a verification framework that takes a different route: translating Rust to verification-friendly C to exploit the maturity of existing C verification infrastructure. Our pipeline extends Charon (Rust to LLBC) and Eurydice (LLBC to C) with broader Rust feature support, then employs Frama-C for deductive verification with LLM-based contract inference to reduce manual annotation overhead. Applied to a production component from Huawei’s HarmonyOS, HiRustVer successfully translates the entire codebase—handling associated types, dynamic dispatch, closures, and unsafe blocks—and achieves 56% automated verification, with the remainder under expert review. This work demonstrates that formal verification of real-world, non-verification-oriented Rust codebases is achievable today with appropriate tooling and engineering effort.

Rust has emerged as the dominant memory-safe low-level / efficient systems programming language, combining compile-time ownership guarantees with C/C++-level performance. Major projects including the Linux kernel, Android, Windows, and cloud infrastructure increasingly incorporate Rust components. However, Rust’s type system cannot prevent all errors: panics from arithmetic overflow, logic errors in complex algorithms, and undefined behavior from unsafe code require formal verification for mission-critical systems.

We report on our ongoing effort to verify a production Rust component from HarmonyOS, Huawei’s operating system for IoT and mobile devices, which aims to be the first successful industrial-scale verification of a real-world Rust codebase developed without verification in mind.

The Industrial Verification Challenge. Driven by this practical case study, we identify key challenges in industrial Rust verification that differ from academic tool development, which are mainly threefold.

Feature coverage Real codebases pervasively use advanced features not designed to be verification-friendly, which may even be more common than expected in practice as many of them hide behind everyday standard library functionalities. For example, associated types (easily encountered with iterators), dynamic dispatch via dyn traits (in printing / formatting), closures (in collection operations), and unsafe blocks for performance. This calls for comprehensive feature coverage in the potential verification toolchain.

Complex external dependencies Projects depend on hundreds of crates with deeply nested graphs; our target component alone transitively depends on over a hundred crates, making whole-program verification infeasible.

Industrial constraints Beyond the codebase challenges, industrial realities impose additional constraints: Code rewriting is infeasible (requiring abstract model construction, equivalence validation, extensive cross-team coordination, and risking functional regressions). Human effort is expensive; automation is essential for feasibility and timely delivery, favoring practical effectiveness over theoretical elegance. Tools must be robust and production-ready—handling real code, providing predictable performance, and not crashing on industrial inputs—rather than merely solving toy examples or demonstrating theoretical completeness.

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Status of Existing Tools. After an extensive survey, we find that no existing Rust verification tool satisfies these combined requirements. We summarize the principal tools and their limitations below.

Kani [13] is a bounded model checker employing symbolic execution to verify properties within bounded scopes. Its bounded nature fundamentally limits applicability: unbounded loops and data structures cause divergence or incomplete coverage, rendering it insufficient for industrial-scale verification where properties must hold over arbitrary inputs.

Prusti [1] is a deductive verifier built on the Viper framework. While promising, it faces restricted support for unsafe code, robustness and efficiency challenges on complex real-world code, and inadequate support for closures—features pervasive in industrial Rust codebases.

Verus [11] is a deductive verifier for proving functional correctness through specifications written in a verification-friendly subset. It typically requires substantial code rewriting to conform to its supported subset, and notably excludes closures and dyn traits, violating the industrial constraint of minimal code modification.

RustBelt [8] is a semantic framework for reasoning about Rust’s type system and unsafe code using separation logic. While theoretically principled, it requires substantial manual proof effort with limited automation and operates on a restricted subset of Rust features.

Aeneas [5] translates Rust to a lambda-calculus-based formalism for verification. The tool remains in early development with insufficient support for unsafe code, limited support for loops, and no support for closures.

VeriFast [7] is a modular verifier supporting C, Rust and Java; for Rust, it targets unsafe code but remains at an early stage, lacking closures and dyn traits.

Hax [4] extracts Rust code to formal backends for verification, but faces limited support for dyn traits, difficulties translating certain constructs (such as `&mut` returns), and insufficient automation.

MIRI [9] is one of the most mature tools as a dynamic execution engine and sanitizer that detects undefined behavior at runtime. However, as a dynamic tool, it validates only specific executions rather than proving properties for all possible inputs, and checks a fixed set of behaviors rather than serving as a general-purpose verifier.

Our Approach: Verification via Mature C Toolchains. Given these challenges, instead of building Rust-native verification tools from scratch, we translate Rust to verification-friendly C and reuse the well-established C verification infrastructure built over the past decades. Although translation increases code size by making implicit behavior explicit, this aids verification by exposing control flow and data representations.

We choose C and Frama-C as the verification backend for several reasons. Today, industrial verification ecosystems for C are significantly more mature than their Rust-native counterparts in terms of tool stability, automation, and integration into large-scale workflows. Frama-C offers a modular plugin ecosystem and supports automation-oriented verification workflows, providing a practical path to incremental verification: the verifier can be re-run efficiently on modified modules, making it compatible with industrial development cycles. Our team also has extensive experience with C verification and Frama-C, which is crucial for industrial feasibility.

Our three-stage pipeline handles the required advanced features:

Stage 1: Rust to LLBC via Charon. We extended Charon [6], which extracts Rust to the LLBC (Low-Level Borrow-Checked) intermediate representation. The LLBC IR resembles a simplified and structured MIR with passes that make the representation more verification-friendly. Charon originally supported a number of advanced features and could translate a good portion of real-world Rust code, and has been adopted in some recent work [2]. We further refined Charon to provide monomorphized LLBC, vtable generation for dyn traits, and closure encoding, which proved necessary for handling our target codebase. These features are encoded explicitly and structurally in LLBC, making them more amenable to subsequent C-level reasoning. For example, the closure structures and their virtual implementation of the Fn-series traits are made explicit data types and trait implementations in LLBC, and the implicit list of functions for the vtables are made explicit structs with function pointers.

Stage 2: LLBC to C via Eurydice. Eurydice [6] is then employed to translate LLBC to C via the KaReMeL [3] toolchain. Originally designed to couple with the Charon toolchain, the tool produces C code of the best quality among all existing Rust-to-C translators [12] we surveyed. However, it handled only a limited set of Rust features. To make it work for our target, we made substantial extensions, including higher-order support, refined array handling, and comprehensive handling of dynamically-sized types (DSTs).

Translation Example. To illustrate how the pipeline makes implicit Rust semantics explicit, consider a simple closure capturing a local variable:

Rust (source)

```
fn apply(offset: i32, x: i32) -> i32 {
  let add = |v: i32| v + offset;
  add(x)
}
```

C (generated)

```
typedef struct {
  int32_t offset; // captured env
} closure_add_env_t;

int32_t closure_add_call(closure_add_env_t *env, int32_t v) {
  return v + env->offset;
}

int32_t apply(int32_t offset, int32_t x) {
  closure_add_env_t env = { offset };
  return closure_add_call(&env, x);
}
```

The Rust closure is desugared into an explicit environment struct holding captured variables, and the closure call is translated to a regular function call receiving the environment as a parameter. Similarly, dyn trait objects become vtable structs with function pointers, and iterators are lowered into explicit loop constructs with bounds checking. This explicit encoding, while increasing code size, exposes all control flow and data operations to Frama-C’s reasoning engine.

Stage 3: Verification via Frama-C and PREGUESS. We verify generated C using Frama-C’s WP plugin for deductive verification of the so-called *RunTime Errors* (RTE) properties [10]. To reduce manual ACSL annotation overhead, we employ PREGUESS, an LLM-based contract inference tool. We applied engineering techniques to improve LLM effectiveness: shortening mangled identifiers to fit context windows, conservatively splitting large functions into smaller verification units, and replacing complex macros with explicit argument-checking computations. Notably, the translated project still presents significant challenges for PREGUESS, due to the rather complex control flows from Rust translation. To address them, we also revised PREGUESS to better cope with the automation task.

Current Status. We successfully translated the entire target HarmonyOS component, handling all advanced features: associated types in iterators, dyn-based formatting, closure-heavy collections, and `unsafe` blocks. Frama-C’s WP plugin automatically generated verification conditions for RTE. With PREGUESS, we now achieve **56% automation**, automatically generating contracts for external functions. The remaining 44% requires manual specification of complex invariants, which is currently under expert review. We expect to complete manual verification in the near term, providing end-to-end memory-safety and panic-freedom guarantees for critical entry points.

Contributions Summary. In summary, our contributions are:

- (1) an industrial verification case study on a real, non-verification-oriented Rust codebase under realistic constraints;
- (2) a new, tool-assisted verification path that makes such verification feasible today;
- (3) substantial extensions to Charon and Eurydice to support additional mainstream Rust features; and,
- (4) adaptation of Eurydice and PREGUESS to enable (semi-)automated, modular verification of the generated C code using Frama-C.

Limitations and Future Work. Our current approach has limitations at three levels. At the *engineering level*, Charon and Eurydice do not yet cover all Rust features encountered in arbitrary codebases. Notably, on this front, the standard library is the immediate yet ultimate challenge—it is used so pervasively and its internal implementations use almost all advanced features. At the *trust-base level*, the translation pipeline is part of the TCB; formal correctness proofs or certified compilation would strengthen assurance. At the *technical level*, our approach suits concrete application entry points rather than generic libraries in full generality (unbounded polymorphism requires reasoning about all instantiations); modular verification workflows for generic LLBC before monomorphization would extend applicability.

The Rust-to-C translation typically increases code size, which is not merely an artifact of poor engineering but largely reflects the need to make Rust’s implicit structure explicit for a C-level reasoning engine (e.g., explicit control-flow and data representations from monomorphization, desugaring, and vtable generation).

We plan several directions for future work. First, we aim to extend Charon toward broader Rust feature coverage, with an emphasis on stability and predictable behavior on large dependency graphs. Second, we plan to align the translation pipeline with modular verification needs by basing the workflow on monomorphized LLBC, reducing friction when verifying across module boundaries. Third, we plan to support Rust-level functional specifications and annotations, including reusable generic specifications that can be instantiated across multiple monomorphizations, and to model relevant portions of the standard library at the specification level. Fourth, to reduce the trust burden, we plan to formalize and prove key correctness properties of the MIR-to-C translation, such as a backward simulation argument for the verified subset. As Rust-native verification backends mature and become industrially viable, the framework can evolve toward a backend-agnostic toolchain that eventually switches to Rust-native backends while preserving the modular workflow.

This case study shows that formal verification of real-world, non-verification-oriented Rust codebases is within reach today, and that the translation-based approach offers a practical path forward under industrial constraints.

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